

Numerical algorithm for phase portrait generation using vector fields, nullclines, and trajectories

Description:

Pseudocode to reproduce figure 4 of manuscript number **EPJS-D-25-00637R3**.

The parameter set is mentioned in the manuscript.

The phase portraits are constructed by combining vector field visualization, nullcline analysis, and numerical trajectories. For each parameter set, the vector field is evaluated on a uniform grid and displayed to illustrate local flow directions. Prey and predator nullclines are computed from the steady-state conditions of the governing equations. Solution trajectories are then generated from multiple initial conditions using a numerical ODE solver and superimposed on the phase plane. This approach allows qualitative assessment of stability, equilibrium structure, and long-term dynamics.

Implementation note. The procedure can be implemented in MATLAB using built-in routines: `meshgrid` and `quiver` for vector fields, `fplot` or numerical root detection for nullclines, and `ode45` for trajectory integration. No specialized toolboxes are required beyond standard MATLAB; the Symbolic Math Toolbox is optional for analytic nullcline plotting.

Pseudocode 6 Numerical algorithm for phase portrait

- 1: **Input:** Model equations $\dot{H} = F(H, P)$, $\dot{P} = G(H, P)$
 - 2: **Input:** Parameter set and phase domain $(H, P) \in [0, H_{\max}] \times [0, P_{\max}]$
 - 3: **Input:** Set of initial conditions $\{(H_0, P_0)\}$
 - 4: Generate a uniform grid over the phase domain
 - 5: Evaluate $F(H, P)$ and $G(H, P)$ at each grid point
 - 6: Normalize the vector field for visualization
 - 7: Plot the vector field in the phase plane
 - 8: Compute prey nullcline from $F(H, P) = 0$
 - 9: Compute predator nullcline from $G(H, P) = 0$
 - 10: Plot nullclines in the phase plane
 - 11: **for** each initial condition (H_0, P_0) **do**
 - 12: Numerically integrate the system over a sufficiently long time interval
 - 13: Plot the resulting trajectory in phase space
 - 14: Mark the initial point
 - 15: **end for**
 - 16: **Output:** Phase portrait showing vector field, nullclines, and trajectories
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